

Strategies Adopted by Cross-Border Traders in Response to the Closure of the Benin-Niger Border (July 2023-2025)

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Abstract:

This article analyzes the strategies adopted by cross-border traders to continue their activities despite the closure of the border between Benin and Niger, which began in July 2023 and remains in effect in 2025. It relies on secondary sources such as press articles, NGO reports, and academic publications. The study highlights the different methods used by traders to sustain trade and cope with the economic and social constraints imposed by the closure.

Keywords: Cross-border traders, Benin-Niger border, adaptation strategies, economic resilience, border crisis.

Introduction

Since the military coup that occurred in Niger in July 2023, the border between Benin and Niger has been closed, causing major disruptions in trade and affecting the economic life of border regions. This situation has particularly impacted cross-border traders who rely on the movement of goods to provide for their livelihoods and those of their families. Several studies have already examined different aspects of this crisis. The Global Initiative Against Transnational Organized Crime (GI-TOC, 2024), in its study entitled *The Closure of the Border Between Benin and Niger Increases Profits from Migrant Smuggling*, focused on the rise of smuggling activities and the adaptation of informal actors to migrant trafficking. Similarly, Le360 Afrique (2024), in the article *Niger-Benin: Border Closure Ruins Economic Exchanges*, presented the difficulties faced by Nigerien traders in accessing blocked goods and the economic consequences of the closure. The ARTE.tv (2024) report, *Benin: Trade*

Blocked with Niger, illustrated the impact on truck drivers and traders, with many trucks immobilized in Malanville. Furthermore, the African Scientific Journal (2024) published *Functioning of Cross-Border Agricultural Markets in the Niger Valley*, analyzing the repercussions on local agricultural markets and the general strategies of traders to sustain their activities, while the *Revue Geovision* (2024), in *Strategies of Traders Facing Crises and Uncertainties of Trade in Two Cross-Border Areas of Benin-Niger and Nigeria*, examined the general adaptations of traders in border regions during times of crisis. As these authors have already addressed economic impacts, smuggling, local markets, and the general adaptation of traders, it remains to study the specific strategies adopted by cross-border traders to continue their activities despite the border closure, an aspect that has been little explored in the literature. This is why we focus on the topic: *Strategies Adopted by Cross-Border Traders in Response to the Closure of the Benin-Niger Border (July 2023 – 2025)*. The chosen chronological framework corresponds to the start of the closure in July 2023 and extends to the year 2025, in order to allow for a comprehensive observation of traders' adaptations over a sufficiently recent and continuous period, making it possible to analyze the evolving strategies in response to the prolonged closure of the border. For this study, we carried out research in several libraries in Cotonou, including the CAEB, the National Library of Benin, and the Benin Excellence Library. We also spoke with some cross-border traders to gather direct information on their experiences and strategies. The analysis is mainly based on secondary sources such as press articles, NGO reports, and academic publications, complemented by these observations and testimonies. The article will be structured into three parts: first, the context and issues of the closure of the Benin-Niger border; second, the strategies adopted by cross-border traders; and third, the economic and social consequences of these strategies as well as the prospects for cross-border trade.

1- Context and Issues of the Closure of the Benin-Niger Border

The border between Benin and Niger was closed in July 2023 following the military coup that occurred in Niger, causing major disruptions in trade and affecting the economic life of border regions. This closure directly impacted cross-border traders, who depend on the movement of goods to meet their needs and those of their families. According to the report by the Global Initiative Against Transnational Organized Crime (GI-TOC, 2024), the closure of the border encouraged the rise of smuggling activities and forced some economic actors to seek alternatives to sustain their trade. Similarly, *Le360 Afrique* (2024) emphasizes that this closure caused a shortage of products and an increase in prices in local markets, heavily

affecting the daily lives of traders and consumers. ARTE.tv (2024) reports that many trucks carrying goods were stranded in Malanville, leading to considerable economic losses. The African Scientific Journal (2024) also shows that local agricultural markets were disrupted, forcing traders to adapt their practices to continue their activities. Finally, the Revue Geovision (2024) indicates that, in cross-border areas, traders developed general strategies of adaptation in the face of uncertainties and difficulties linked to the closure. These different studies show that the closure of the border concerns not only the economy but also affects the social dimension and the organization of local exchanges. Thus, understanding the context and issues of this closure is essential to analyze how cross-border traders develop specific strategies to maintain their activity and ensure their economic survival.

2- Strategies Adopted by Cross-Border Traders

In response to the closure of the border between Benin and Niger, cross-border traders have had to demonstrate ingenuity to continue their activities. According to the report by the Global Initiative Against Transnational Organized Crime (GI-TOC, 2024), some traders resorted to using local intermediaries to buy and sell goods within the border area, thereby reducing the need to officially cross the border. Le360 Afrique (2024) notes that other traders diversified their products in order to meet the immediate needs of the local market, minimizing losses linked to blocked goods. ARTE.tv (2024) also highlights that systems of communication and coordination among traders were established to organize deliveries and share information on checkpoints or accessible areas. The African Scientific Journal (2024) mentions that some actors developed solidarity networks, helping each other to transport, store, and sell products despite the restrictions. These strategies show that traders do not simply endure the effects of the closure but actively adapt their practices to maintain their activity, protect their income, and ensure the continuity of trade in a difficult context.

3- Economic and Social Consequences of the Adopted Strategies

The strategies implemented by cross-border traders have significant economic and social impacts. According to Le360 Afrique (2024), product diversification and the use of local intermediaries have helped to limit certain financial losses, but traders continue to experience a significant decrease in their income. ARTE.tv (2024) highlights that the use of communication and coordination networks has strengthened solidarity among traders, creating new forms of local organization and cooperation. The African Scientific Journal (2024) indicates that these adaptations also affect consumers, notably through price fluctuations and

reduced availability of certain products in the markets. Furthermore, the Revue Geovision (2024) shows that these strategies may lead to increased dependence on certain intermediaries and informal networks, which transforms traditional commercial practices. In sum, although these strategies allow traders to continue their activities despite the border closure, they result in both limited economic benefits and significant social changes in the way cross-border trade is organized.

Conclusion

The closure of the border between Benin and Niger, which occurred in July 2023, has profoundly disrupted cross-border trade and the economic life of the affected regions. This study has highlighted the strategies adopted by traders to continue their activities despite the constraints imposed by this closure. It appears that traders have developed various adaptation methods, such as using intermediaries, diversifying their products, and establishing solidarity networks to maintain commercial exchanges.

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Bibliography

• **Academic Articles and Reports**

1. Zato, C. L., & Yabi, J. (2024). *Income of Agro-Food Producers and Traders in the Niger Valley: Influence of Border Closures*. IJAFAME Journal, 31 p.
2. African Scientific Journal (2023). *Functioning of Cross-Border Agricultural Markets in the Niger Valley* 7 p.

• **News Articles**

3. ARTE.tv (2024). *Benin: Trade Blocked with Niger*.
4. Le360 Afrique (2024). *Closure of Borders between Benin and Niger: A Real Obstacle for the Dendi Ganda Cross-Border Consultation Framework*.
5. Le Monde (2024). *Closed Border, Blocked Oil: Tensions Rise Between Niger and Benin*.

• **International Organization Reports**

6. Global Initiative Against Transnational Organized Crime (GI-TOC) (2024). *The Closure of the Border between Benin and Niger Increases Profits from Migrant Smuggling*.
7. Friedrich Ebert Stiftung (FES) (2024). *Closure of Borders Between Benin and Niger*.

• **Bibliography**

- <https://revue.ijafame.com/index.php/home/article/view/1305> ce 11/02/2025 .
- <https://africanscientificjournal.com/index.php/AfricanScientificJournal/article/download/685/622/705> ce 11/02/2025
- <https://www.arte.tv/fr/videos/116489-000-A/benin-commerce-bloque-avec-le-niger/> ce 25/02/2025
- <https://www.civita-niger.org/fr/node/382> ce 25/02/2025
- https://www.lemonde.fr/afrique/article/2024/06/10/frontiere-fermee-petrole-bloque-la-tension-monte-entre-le-niger-et-le-benin_6238463_3212.html ce 03/5/2025
- <https://riskbulletins.globalinitiative.net/wea-obs-011/fr/04-benin-niger-border-closure-drives-surge-migrant-smuggling-profits.html> ce 03/05/2025

- <https://www.fes.de/fr/themenportal-flucht-migration-integration/page-darticles-fuite-migration-integration/fermeture-des-frontieres-entre-le-benin-et-le-nigerce> 06/07/2025